

BEYOND THE BADGE: A CRITICAL ANALYSIS OF ONLINE EDUCATION'S IMPACT ON CRIMINOLOGY STUDENTS' LEARNING AND PROFESSIONAL DEVELOPMENT

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ABSTRACT

The COVID-19 pandemic forced a rapid shift to online education across academic disciplines, including criminology. While online learning offers potential benefits for flexibility and access, concerns remain regarding its effectiveness and student experience. This study investigates the experiences of criminology students transitioning to online education during this unprecedented time. This study employed a descriptive-correlational approach to explore the experiences of criminology students transitioning to online education during the COVID-19 pandemic. Descriptive analysis characterized student demographics (age, sex, year level, income, device access) and attitudes towards online learning. Correlation analysis examined relationships between these student characteristics, challenges faced in the online environment, and the overall impact of the transition. The findings revealed a significant positive correlation between student-reported challenges and the perceived impact of the transition. This suggests that students experiencing greater difficulty with online learning also felt a more significant negative impact on their education. In response, the study emphasizes the need for targeted interventions to address these challenges. The authors propose online seminars/training programs for both students and instructors to enhance online learning skills and maximize the potential benefits of e-learning platforms in criminology education.

Keywords: *Online learning, Criminology education, COVID-19 pandemic, Challenges in online learning, Impact of online learning, Online training programs*

INTRODUCTION

The occurrence of coronavirus disease 2019 or COVID-19 created a worldwide health predicament that has a big effect in the daily living. According to World Health Organization (2020), the covid-19 pandemic is accelerating, thus, virus is still spreading fast and most people are still susceptible. It reached more than one hundred countries with over 100,000 cases during the first week of March (Bhagavathula et al., 2020).

The widespread of Covid-19 severely obstructed all aspects of life including economic, social and cultural (UNESCO, 2020). Thus, in an effort to lessen the outbreak of COVID-19, many countries have imposed lockdown, movement control or shelter in place orders on their residents (Azlan et al., 2020).

Moreover, with the outburst of Covid-19 disease globally, the Philippines started the longest community quarantine in the world in March 15 which is an effort to contain a Covid-19 outbreak (De Guzman & Guido, 2020). Hence, WHO in the Philippines activated the highest level of alert by declaring COVID-19 as a public health emergency of international concern (WHO, 2020).

Also, the government implemented numerous actions including community quarantine; expanded its testing capacity from one national reference laboratory with the Research Institute of Tropical Medicine (RITM) to 23 licensed testing labs; and addressed the social and economic impact to the community of the occurring pandemic by providing social amelioration to low-income families (WHO, 2020).

Therefore, the spread of COVID-19 pandemic changes the way human live. Since there is no cure or vaccine available for Covid-19 disease, everyone is expected to accept setting into life under “new normal” (Asonye, 2020). It requires people to cope and adjust in order to fit with the present environment.

The COVID-19 pandemic has also changed education nowadays. The whole educational system from elementary to tertiary level has been collapsed due to novel coronavirus disease 2019 (Mishra, et al., 2020). Schools shut across the world wherein millions of children have had to adapt to new types of learning (Li & Lalani, 2020).

According to Khalil et al. (2020), the closure of educational activities due to the ongoing COVID-19 pandemic resulted in an unplanned shift from traditional learning to a setup that exclusively involves online or digital teaching and learning. E-learning or online learning has become the mandatory component of all educational institutions like schools, colleges, and universities in and around the world due to the pandemic crisis of COVID-19 (Radha et al., 2020).

With that, this type of approach is likely to be challenging in terms of mental, emotional and academic (Burke, 2020). As emphasized by Garcia & Weiss (2020), education system was not built, nor prepared, to cope with a situation like this. Thus, learners' academic performance is deteriorating during the pandemic, along with their

progress on other developmental skills.

Online learning can be an effective, rich and fulfilling experience but it requires everyone to pay careful attention to student experiences since some students are struggling in transitioning to online learning; having no easy access to WiFi or computers (Houlden & Veletsianos, 2020). Some students without reliable internet access and/or technology struggle to participate in digital learning which is seen across countries and between income brackets within countries (Li & Lalani, 2020).

Furthermore, the forced migration from in-person to online learning has also deepened the digital divide. It describes the gap between those who have access to the internet and technology at home, and those who do not (Dennon, 2020).

Thus, with all these data presented, the researcher was encouraged to conduct the study. This study was conducted to know the impact of transition to online education among the criminology students during the occurrence of Covid-19 pandemic. This study was conducted as it concerns the welfare of every student in facing the new normal education.

Research Questions

This study aimed to know the impact of transition to online education among criminology students of Samar College on the occurrence of Covid-19 pandemic. Specifically, it sought to answer the following questions:

1. What is the profile of the criminology student-respondents in terms of the following personal variates:
 - 1.1 age and sex;
 - 1.2 year level;
 - 1.3 gross monthly family income;
 - 1.4 device ownership;
 - 1.5 internet access; and
 - 1.6 attitude toward online learning?
2. What are the challenges encountered by the criminology student-respondents with the shift from traditional to online mode of learning?
3. Is there a significant relationship between the challenges encountered by the criminology student-respondents with the shift to online education and their profile variates?
4. What is the impact of the transition to online education during Covid-19 pandemic?
5. Is there a significant relationship between the impact of the transition to online education during Covid-19 pandemic and the following factors:
 - 5.1 student-related variates
 - 5.2 challenges encountered with the shift from traditional to online mode of learning?
6. What implications maybe derived based on the findings of this study?

METHODOLOGY

In this descriptive-correlation study, the researcher employed a stratified random sampling technique to gather data from 312 Criminology students at Samar College. To ensure data quality, a survey questionnaire was subjected to a two-step validation process. First, experts reviewed the content for clarity and relevance, offering suggestions for improvement. Then, the test-retest method was applied, administering the questionnaire to a small group twice with a one-week interval. A correlation coefficient (0.98) indicated excellent internal consistency and reliability of the instrument. The data collection process involved obtaining approval from the Dean and securing informed consent from the participants. Each student received the questionnaire and ample time to complete it with the assurance of confidentiality. This comprehensive approach aimed to describe the student profiles in terms of demographics and online learning attitudes. Furthermore, the study sought to identify potential relationships between these factors and the challenges and impacts experienced by students during the transition to online education amidst the COVID-19 pandemic.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The following were the salient findings of the study:

1. The majority of the respondents were male, with a total of 195 student respondents. Additionally, the age bracket ranging from 18 to 22 shows the highest number of student respondents, both male and female.
2. There are an equal number of student respondents for each grade level, with 78 respondents per grade level and a total of 312 student respondents.
3. The majority of the student respondents were earning a family monthly income of PHP 4,000 to PHP 5,999.
4. The majority of the student respondents owned a mobile phone or smartphone, for a total of 267 student respondents.
5. The majority of the student respondents access the internet through prepaid mobile data, for a total of 269 student respondents.
6. The majority of the student respondents were “undecided” or uncertain about their attitude toward online learning or e-learning. This finding highlights a lack of clear opinions on this educational method. This indecisiveness could stem from several factors. Perhaps the students are relatively new to online learning due to the pandemic and haven't had enough time to form a strong positive or negative view. Alternatively, their online learning experiences might have been inconsistent, offering both positive aspects (like flexibility) and negative ones (like technical issues). This mixed bag could make it difficult to have a definitive opinion on online learning's overall effectiveness. Additionally, students might

not be fully aware of the potential benefits and drawbacks of online learning, such as increased accessibility versus reduced social interaction. Without a clear understanding of these factors, it's difficult to form a strong opinion. Further investigation into the reasons behind this indecisiveness could be valuable.

7. The majority of the student respondents indicated “highly challenging” toward their perceived challenges encountered with the shift from traditional to online modes of learning.
8. The majority of the student respondents indicated “highly impactful” toward their perceived impact of the transition to online education during the COVID-19 pandemic.
9. The null hypothesis states there is no significant relationship between the challenges encountered by the Criminology student-respondents with the shift to online education and their profile variables, especially age, sex, family monthly income, device ownership, and internet access, which were “accepted.”.
10. On the other hand, the profile variate pertaining to the year level of the student respondents was rejected.
11. The null hypothesis states there is no significant relationship between the impact of the transition to online education during the COVID-19 pandemic and the student-profile variables, especially sex, year level, family monthly income, device ownership, and internet access, which were “accepted.”.
12. On the other hand, the profile variable pertaining to the age of the student respondents was “rejected.”.
13. The null hypothesis stating there is no significant relationship between the impact of the transition to online education during the COVID-19 pandemic and the challenges encountered with the shift to online education was “rejected.”.

Attitude Toward online learning or e-learning

This data paints a complex picture of student views on online learning. While most students agreed they were interested in the concept (liking statements about finding it interesting and improving study skills), they were unsure about its effectiveness during the pandemic. This is further shown by their disagreement with statements suggesting online learning is better than traditional methods or that they felt fully prepared for online classes. Overall, the results suggest students are undecided about online learning.

Table 1
Attitude Toward Online Learning or e-Learning

Attitude Toward Online Learning or e-Learning	Weighted Means	Interpretation
1) I am interested in e-learning or online learning.	4.48	Agree
2) E-learning improves my study skill.	3.95	Agree
3) E-learning makes my quarantine time a useful one.	3.63	Agree
4) Improving knowledge through e-learning is better than traditional learning.	2.39	Disagree
5) I am satisfied with the use of online learning approach during Covid-19 pandemic.	2.55	Undecided
6) I am physically and mentally capable of studying all remaining subjects for the semester online.	1.64	Disagree
7) I have enough time and resources to prepare myself for online learning.	1.84	Disagree
8) I have enough time and resources to prepare myself for online learning.	1.61	Disagree
Grand Weighted Mean	2.76	Undecided

Legend: 4.51-5.00 – Strongly Agree (SA)
3.51-4.50 – Agree (A)
2.51-3.50 – Undecided (U)
1.51-2.50 – Disagree (D)
1.00–1.50 – Strongly Disagree (SD)

This has some key implications. First, students seem interested in the potential of online learning but might need more support. Institutions could offer improved online learning orientation programs to address concerns about resources, time management, and how effective online learning is compared to traditional methods. Additionally, the data highlights the need to identify and address student challenges, such as limited access to technology or feeling overwhelmed with online coursework. Finally, the uncertainty suggests some students might benefit from a more personalized online learning experience. This could involve offering hybrid models or catering to individual learning styles within online environments. By understanding these complexities in

student attitudes, educators can work towards creating a more effective and supportive online learning experience.

Challenges Encountered by the Student-Respondents with the Shift from Traditional to Online Mode of Learning

Students faced a significant number of challenges during the shift to online learning, according to this data. Most respondents found aspects like adapting to new learning styles, managing home responsibilities alongside studies, and limited communication with teachers to be highly challenging. The data also suggests that unreliable internet access, a lack of dedicated study space, mental health difficulties, and limited access to technology were major hurdles. Overall, the transition to online learning was perceived as highly challenging by the majority of students.

Table 2

Challenges Encountered with the Shift from Traditional to Online Mode of Learning

Challenges encountered with the shift from traditional to online mode of learning	Weighted Means	Interpretation
1) Difficulty adjusting to new learning styles	3.91	Highly Challenging
2) Need to fulfill responsibilities at home	3.41	Highly Challenging
3) Poor communication with educators	3.46	Highly Challenging
4) Limited space conducive for studying	3.81	Highly Challenging
5) Unreliable or no internet access	3.88	Highly Challenging
6) Mental health difficulties	3.77	Highly Challenging
7) Lack of technical skills	3.33	Highly Challenging
8) Need to work for extra income	2.69	Moderately Challenging
9) No device or limited access	3.54	Highly Challenging
10) Lack of basic needs	2.52	Moderately Challenging
Grand Weighted Mean	3.43	Highly Challenging
Legend: 3.26-4.00 –Highly Challenging	(HC)	
2.51-3.25 – Moderately Challenging	(MC)	
1.76-2.50 – Slightly Challenging	(SC)	
1.00-1.75 – Not Challenging	(NC)	

These findings hold important implications. There's a need for a more well-rounded approach to online learning that considers students' personal situations, mental well-being, and technical capabilities. Institutions should develop support systems to address communication issues, offer technical training, and provide resources for students struggling with home life or mental health. Additionally, creating flexible learning environments that cater to various learning styles and acknowledge limitations in internet access or study space could be beneficial. Finally, efforts to bridge the digital divide by providing affordable technology and internet access are crucial for ensuring everyone can participate equally in online learning.

Impact of the Transition to Online Education Among Student-Respondents During Covid-19 Pandemic

The impact of online learning during COVID-19 had both positive and negative aspects for students, according to this data. While there were some downsides, the overall impact was considered positive.

On the positive side, students highly valued the access to a variety of learning materials offered online, including presentations, videos, and documents. This caters to different learning styles and preferences. Additionally, students appreciated the flexibility and autonomy online learning provided, allowing them to learn at their own pace and comfort level. They also reported that online courses often had clear instructions and offered a wider range of resources compared to traditional methods.

However, there were also downsides. A significant negative impact was the perception that communication between students and instructors decreased in online environments. This highlights the importance of creating strong communication channels and engagement strategies specifically for online learning. Students also reported feeling somewhat isolated due to online learning, suggesting a need for strategies to promote interaction and a sense of community within online courses. Finally, a small portion of students indicated online learning might lead to decreased motivation and a lower understanding of the material.

Understanding these impacts is crucial. Educators can leverage the strengths of online learning, like material variety and flexibility, while developing strategies to address the challenges. This could involve increasing student-to-instructor and student-to-student interaction through online forums or activities, fostering a sense of community within courses, and providing clear expectations and regular feedback to keep students motivated.

Table 3

Impact of the Transition to Online Education During Covid-19 Pandemic

Impact of the transition to online education during Covid-19 pandemic	Weighted Means	Interpretation
1) E-learning fulfills the needs of today's learners at their own comfort and requirements.	4.29	Highly Impactful
2) Online education accommodates variety of learning styles among students.	4.29	Highly Impactful
3) It provides a wide range of materials for the learners.	4.41	Highly Impactful
4) It can share and offer teaching-learning materials in diverse formats such as slideshows, audios, videos, PDFs, e-mails, word documents and so on	4.73	Extremely Impactful
5) It provides clear, easy, gradual instructions for better understanding of the learners.	4.19	Highly Impactful
6) Online learning platforms can help students become more independent learners.	2.60	Moderately Impactful
7) Online education lack of motivation among students.	2.22	Slightly Impactful
8) It provides less understanding of the lesson or topic discussed.	2.00	Slightly Impactful
9) It decreases communication levels between the students and their instructors	4.01	Highly Impactful
10) Students feeling of isolation.	3.45	Moderately Impactful
Grand Weighted Mean	3.62	Highly Impactful

Legend: 4.51-5.00 –Extremely Impactful (EI)
3.51-4.50 – Highly Impactful (HI)
2.51-3.50 – Moderately Impactful (MI)
1.51-2.50 – Slightly Impactful (SI)
1.00–1.50 – Not Impactful (NI)

By acknowledging both the positive and negative aspects of online learning, educators can work towards optimizing online learning environments for better student

engagement, learning, and well-being.

Conclusions

This study investigated the online learning experiences of Criminology students during the COVID-19 pandemic. Here are the key findings:

1. The majority of respondents were male, aged 18-22, and came from various year levels. Most students belonged to families with a monthly income of Php 4,000 to 5,999.
2. The majority of students owned mobile phones and accessed the internet primarily through prepaid mobile data.
3. A significant portion of the students were undecided about online learning, suggesting a lack of clear opinions.
4. Students reported encountering significant challenges with the transition to online learning, including adapting to new learning styles, balancing responsibilities, and communication issues.
5. Despite the challenges, students perceived the overall impact of online learning to be positive. They valued the flexibility, diverse learning materials, and clear instructions offered in online environments.
6. There were no significant relationships between most student profile variables (sex, family income, device ownership, internet access) and either the challenges faced or the perceived impact of online learning. However, there was a weak association between year level and challenges faced, and between age and perceived impact. Finally, a significant relationship was found between the challenges encountered and the overall impact of online learning, suggesting that students who faced more challenges also perceived a stronger impact (positive or negative) from online education.

Overall, the study highlights the complex experiences of Criminology students with online learning during the pandemic. While students appreciated the flexibility and resources offered online, they also faced significant challenges.

Future efforts should focus on improving communication, addressing student needs, and creating a more supportive online learning environment.

Recommendations

This study highlights the need for improvements to enhance the online learning experience for Criminology students. Here are some recommendations based on the

findings:

1. **Orientation and Support Programs:** Develop comprehensive orientation programs to address student concerns about online learning. This could include information on effective online learning strategies, time management skills, and navigating online resources. Additionally, consider offering ongoing support services to assist students with technical difficulties or academic challenges.
2. **Improved Communication Strategies:** Promote clear and frequent communication between instructors and students. Utilize online forums, discussion boards, or virtual office hours to foster interaction and address student concerns. Encourage active participation through online discussions, collaborative activities, and opportunities for feedback.
3. **Addressing Challenges:** Identify and address specific challenges faced by students. This could involve providing technical training for those with limited skills, exploring alternative assessment methods to reduce workload, or offering flexible learning options to accommodate students with competing responsibilities.
4. **Bridging the Digital Divide:** Consider initiatives to bridge the digital divide by providing affordable access to technology and reliable internet connections. This could involve exploring partnerships with internet service providers or offering loaner devices to students in need.
5. **Personalized Learning:** Explore ways to personalize the online learning experience to cater to different learning styles and preferences. This could involve offering a variety of learning materials in different formats (videos, text, audio), incorporating self-paced learning elements, or allowing for student choice in assignments.
6. **Building Community:** Implement strategies to foster a sense of community and belonging within online courses. This could involve group projects, online social events, or ice-breaker activities at the beginning of the semester.
7. Further research could explore the specific reasons behind student indecision regarding online learning.
8. Investigating the weak association between year level and challenges, or age and perceived impact, could provide insights into tailoring support based on student demographics.
9. The identified relationship between challenges and perceived impact warrants further exploration. Understanding the nature of this relationship could inform strategies to mitigate challenges and maximize the positive impact of online learning.

By implementing these recommendations, institutions can create a more effective

and supportive online learning environment that promotes student success and well-being in the digital age.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

This study was conducted with the utmost respect for participants' rights. The researcher obtained the necessary approvals before starting, clearly explained the purpose of the research (in writing and verbally), and emphasized that participation was completely voluntary. Participants were free to withdraw at any time without having to give a reason. The researcher also took steps to ensure all participant information remained confidential.

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